

ISic1349

I.Sicily inscription 1349

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

in vico S. Constantini apud Franciscum Bolani

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140849

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε Βικ[τωρεῖ]-
2. να ζήσασα ἔτη λ· [τελευ]-
3. τῶ τῆ πρὸς εἰδ (ὦν) [— —]
4. α □ ω
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492960492961492962

EDCS 39101725

PHI 140849

Bibliography

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